

Separation of the Effect of Solvent Structure on the Kinetics of Base Hydrolysis of 3-Bromothicoumarin and Thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate into Contributions to Initial and Transition States

EZZ-ELDIN A. ABU-GHARIB

Science and Math. Center, Chemistry Department, P. O. Box 4341, Riyadh-11491, Saudi Arabia

Manuscript received 19 August 1991, revised 16 November 1992, accepted 2 December 1992

Solubilities of 3-bromothicoumarin (BrSCO) and thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate salts are reported for aqueous solutions and aqueous methanol mixtures. Gibb's free energy of transfer of (BrSCO) and (SCOC⁻) anion are calculated from its solubilities. Method of calculating the transfer chemical potentials of single ions are based on the TPTB assumption. Single ion transfer parameters point out the importance of ion size and hydrophilic/hydrophobic character in determining solvation of ions in binary aqueous mixtures. Transfer chemical potentials of uncharged molecules and ions clue about the sulphur atom is more hydrophobic character than oxygen atom. Base hydrolysis of thiocoumarin derivatives in aqueous methanol mixtures are studied kinetically. Kinetic data lead to Gibb's free energies of activation. Derived transfer parameters are used in the analysis of the kinetic data describing the influence of solvent composition on the initial and transition states. The consequent differences in initial and transition state analyses of reactivities are explored by using TPTB method and by using Wells' solvents-sorting procedures.

The chemistry of thiocoumarin has mostly been neglected compared to that of coumarins and related system. Meth-Cohn and Tarnowski¹ reviewed the chemistry of this system. The pharmaceutical uses of thiocoumarins are numerous.

In continuation of our work on chromone and coumarin derivatives^{2,3}, we report here the effects of solvent on kinetics of base hydrolysis of 3-bromothicoumarin and thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate anion in water and in water co-solvent mixtures. The influence of solvent composition on kinetic parameters is discussed to illustrate the solvation of reactants and of the transition state.

Analysis of solvent effects on reactivity into initial state and transition state components, has been carried out on a variety of organometallic reactions, some substitution reactions and few organic reactions. These analyses are recently documented elsewhere³⁻⁵. In this approach we discuss the initial state—transition state analyses of solvent effect on reactivities of thiocoumarin and thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate anion. We also try to show how these can provide complementary information on the role of solvation, and how transition state modelling may assist in interpretation.

Results and Discussion

The hydrolysis of (BrSCO) and (SCOC⁻) anion with sodium hydroxide at 298 K was followed spectrophotometrically. It can be inferred from the spectra that the hydrolysis takes place in one stage and leads to the opening of the pyrone ring and the formation of a salt of thiocoumarinic acid.

where, x=Br or COOH

The hydrolysis of (BrSCO) and (SCOC⁻) follow first order kinetics over at least three half-life times, under the condition where concentrations of the thiocoumarin derivatives are appropriate to spectrophotometric monitoring and sodium hydroxide is present in large excess. The observed first order rate constants as a function of sodium hydroxide concentration and of methanol percentage for (SCOC⁻) are reported in Table 1, in which each entry represents the mean of at least two acceptably consistent determination. The kinetic results conform to the pattern of equation (1),

$$-d[\text{compound}]/dt = k_{\text{obs}}[\text{compound}] \quad (1)$$

The dependence of k_{obs} on base concentration is indeed linear and there is no significant intercept of the correlation line. Hence the hydrolysis follow the rate law with

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_2 [\text{OH}^-] \quad (2)$$

k_2 is the second order rate constant where $[\text{OH}^-] \gg [\text{compound}]$. This equation indicates that the second order process is dominant in the present solvent mixtures. Values of k_2 are computed from a linear least-squares program of the dependence of observed rate constants on base concentration at each aqueous methanol proportion. The change in the activation barrier $\Delta \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger$ for (SCOC⁻) and (BrSCO) from water to methanol water mixtures are derived in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS FOR BASE HYDROLYSIS OF THIOCOUMARIN-3-CARBOXYLATE IN WATER-METHANOL MIXTURE, DERIVED k_2 AND CALCULATED $\Delta \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger$

[OH ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	Methanol (%)			
	0	20	40	60
0.005	6.1	3.5	2.3	1.7
0.01	12.3	7.3	6.2	3.1
0.02	23.3	15.3	9.5	6.2
0.03	35.0	22.5	14.1	8.8
$k_2 (\times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$	11.66	7.17	4.70	3.06
$\Delta \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$		1.1	2.3	3.4

TABLE 2— k_2 AND $\Delta \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger$ FOR 3-BROMOTHIOCOUMARIN IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURE

$k_2 (\times 10 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$	Methanol (%)		
	20	40	60
	73.1	34.8	12.4
$\Delta \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger (\text{kJ mol}^{-1}, \text{ex. } 20\%)^a$		1.8	4.4

^a3-Bromothiocommarin does not dissolve in water, so used 20% as the reference solvent.

Transfer chemical potentials for thiocommarin can be derived from its solubilities, and the results are shown in Table 3. In order to establish transfer chemical potentials for single ion thiocommarin-3-carboxylate anion, we need the solubilities of a suitable salt in the methanol-water mixtures. Such a salt should be sparingly soluble, so as to minimise activity corrections in calculating transfer chemical potentials, and a cation is required for which transfer chemical potentials are known. Potassium and hexaamminecobalt(III) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ salts of thiocommarin-3-carboxylate are suitable and their solubilities at 298 K are reported in Table 4.

Rate constants of chemical reaction in solvents comprising binary aqueous mixtures depend on the composition of the solvent⁶⁻⁸. Although this dependence may be small or dramatic, it is often

complicated, relatively few pattern emerging. In terms of transition state theory⁹ the complexity reflects the separate influences of changes in solvent composition on initial and transition states. Therefore, independent estimates are sought of the effects of solvent on initial state, the corresponding effects of solvent on transition state being calculated using both kinetic and initial state data. Unfortunately, this apparently simple procedure is best with difficulties, particularly where chemical reaction involves ions. In such cases, extrathermodynamic assumptions have to be invoked in order to calculate single ion properties from measured properties of salts.

TABLE 3—SOLUBILITIES AND INITIAL STATE-TRANSITION STATE ANALYSIS OF SOLVENT EFFECTS ON REACTIVITY TRENDS FOR 3-BROTHIOCOUMARIN (MOLAR SCALE)

10 ⁴ Soly. (BrSCO) (mol dm ⁻³) $\epsilon (\lambda=380) = 8680$	Methanol (% v/v)		
	20	40	60
$\Delta \mu^\ddagger (\text{BrSCO}) (\text{kJ mol}^{-1}, \text{ex } 20\%)$	0.72	2.26	10.88
$\Delta \mu^\ddagger (\text{OH}^-) (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$		-2.8	-6.7
$\Delta \mu^\ddagger (\text{IS}) (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$		0.1	1.6
$\Delta \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$		-2.7	-5.1
$\Delta \mu^\ddagger (\text{TS}) (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$		1.8	4.4
		-0.9	-0.7

For a solution which is dilute in reactant, is the rate constant k_2 is related using transition-state theory⁹ to the molar Gibbs function of activation, $\Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger$, expressed on the *c*-scale at temperature *T*,

$$\ln (k_2 h/kT) = \exp [-\Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger (c\text{-scale}; T)/RT] \quad (3)$$

where, *k* is the Boltzman's constant and *h* is the Plank's constant. We have further assumed that the transmission coefficient is unity and/or independent of solvent composition. If the second order rate constants for a given reaction are $k_{(\text{aq})}$ in aqueous solution and $k_{(x_2)}$ in a solvent mixture (where x_2 is the mole fraction of organic solvent), the effect of added solvent is described using the equation¹⁰,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta(\text{aq} \rightarrow x_2) \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger (\text{SIn}, T; P; c\text{-scale}) \\ = \Delta(\text{aq} \rightarrow x_2) \mu^\ddagger_{\ddagger} (\text{SIn}; T; P; c\text{-scale}) \\ - \Delta(\text{aq} \rightarrow x_2) \mu^\ddagger (\text{A}, \text{SIn}; T; P; c\text{-scale}) \\ - \Delta(\text{aq} \rightarrow x_2) \mu^\ddagger (\text{OH}^-, \text{SIn}; T; P; c\text{-scale}) \end{aligned} \right\} (4)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(\text{aq} \rightarrow x_2) \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger (\text{SIn}; T; P; c\text{-scale}) \\ = RT \ln \{k_{(\text{aq})} / k_{(x_2)}\} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

TABLE 4—SOLUBILITIES OF SCOCK AND [Co(NH₃)₆] (SCOC)₃ AND DERIVED TRANSFER CHEMICAL POTENTIALS FOR (SCOC⁻) ANION ACCORDING TO TPTB AND WELLS

SCOCK Methanol (% v/v)	TPTB				Wells			
	0	20	40	60	0	20	40	60
10 ³ Soly. (SCOCK) (mol dm ⁻³) ε (λ=405)=480	7.21	7.52	7.85	8.17	7.21	7.52	7.85	8.17
Δμ [≠] (SCOCK) (kJ mol ⁻¹)		-0.2	-0.4	-0.6		-0.2	-0.4	-0.6
Δμ [≠] K ⁺ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		2.2	4.3	6.0		0.6	1.0	0.7
Δμ [≠] (SCOC ⁻) (kJ mol ⁻¹)		-2.4	-4.7	-6.6		-0.8	-1.4	-1.3
[Co(NH ₃) ₆] (SCOC) ₃ Methanol (% v/v)	0	20	40	60				
10 ³ Soly. Co(NH ₃) ₆ (SCOC) ₃ (mol dm ⁻³)	6.25	6.98	7.08	8.33				
Δμ [≠] [Co(NH ₃) ₆] (SCOC) ₃ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		-1.1	-1.2	-2.6				
Δμ [≠] [Co(NH ₃) ₆] ³⁺ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		6.5	11.8	15.5				
Δμ [≠] (SCOC ⁻) (kJ mol ⁻¹)		-2.5	-4.3	-6.0				
Mean Δμ [≠] (SCOC ⁻) (kJ mol ⁻¹)		-2.5	-4.5	-6.3				

Δμ[≠](A) and Δμ[≠](OH⁻) are the transfer chemical potentials for organic reactant (A) and (OH⁻) respectively and Δμ[≠] is the transfer chemical potential of the transition state. Here we use the concentration scale, the pressure (P) is ambient and T=298 K. In our work, Δμ[≠] of the reactant can be obtained from the dependence of the solubility of the pure reactant on solvent and Δμ[≠] (OH⁻) is taken from literature^{11,12}.

Although transfer chemical potentials for uncharged (BrSCO) are readily determined using solubility data, such is not the case for ions. The free energy of transfer of a salt of the type M_mX_n, where Mⁿ⁺ is the cation and X^{m-} the anion, from water into a mixture of water co-solvent, is given by the equation,

$$\Delta\mu^{\neq}(M_m X_n) = -RT \ln(k_s/k_w) \quad (6)$$

where k is the solubility of M_mX_n in water (w) and in water co-solvent mixtures (s). The free energy of transfer of the anion Δμ[≠](X^{m-}) can then be calculated from equation (7) using the known values of Δμ[≠](Mⁿ⁺),

$$\Delta\mu^{\neq}(X^{m-}) = \frac{\Delta\mu^{\neq}(M_m X_n) - m\Delta\mu^{\neq}(M^{n+})}{n} \quad (7)$$

In order to establish solvation effects on the chemical potential of (SCOC⁻) anion, we need the solubilities of a suitable salt in water-methanol mixtures. Thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate salts of potassium and hexaminecobalt(III) are sparingly soluble in water and in water-rich methanol mixtures, and transfer chemical potential of K⁺ and [Co(NH₃)₆]³⁺ are known. They are, thus, suitable for the estimation of single ion transfer chemical potentials of (SCOC⁻) anion from water into such mixtures. As discussed earlier¹³ this is probably satisfactory for (Z₊ Z₋) < 3.

The calculation of transfer parameters for ions requires an extrathermodynamic assumption. Granted such an assumption the transfer chemical potentials for a salt can be separated into contributing transfer parameters for ions. Derived transfer parameters should be self-consistent for a range of ions in a given solvent system and for a given ion across a range of aqueous mixtures. However, most treatments of transfer parameters for ions in binary aqueous mixtures favour an assumption which equates transfer parameters for either Ph₄P⁺ and Ph₄B⁻ ions (TPTB) assumption) or Ph₄As⁺ and Ph₄B⁻ ions (TATB assumption). Transfer parameters for ions calculated using one of these assumptions are in close agreement^{11,14}, but do not always agree with those obtained by very different approaches, such as that of Wells.

Values of Δμ[≠]K⁺ and Δμ[≠][Co(NH₃)₆]³⁺ are available from the literature^{2,11}, thus values of Δμ[≠](SCOC⁻) can be calculated from the solubilities of K⁺ and [Co(NH₃)₆]³⁺ salts of (SCOC⁻) in water-methanol mixtures. Table 4 shows that Δμ[≠](SCOC⁻) values from two salts are in good agreement. The mean value of Δμ[≠](SCOC⁻) according to TPTB is compared with transfer chemical potentials for a selection of anions which includes transfer chemical potentials for chromone-3-carboxylate, coumarin-3-carboxylate, picrate, triphenylcyanoboronate and tetraphenylboronate anions^{2,3,11} and illustrated in Fig. 1. The last two anions which contain hydrophobic centers are more markedly stabilised than thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate anion by an increase of methanol content as one would expect on simple electrostatic grounds.

Data of Table 5 show that transfer chemical potentials for thiocoumarin and thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate anion are markedly stabilised than coumarin and coumarin-3-carboxylate anion from aqueous to methanol water mixtures. These results indicate that the sulphur atom character is more hydrophobic than oxygen atom, since the

Fig. 1. Comparison of transfer chemical potentials for thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate with those for another anions; aqueous methanol, 298 K, molar scale.

TABLE 5—TRANSFER CHEMICAL POTENTIALS OF COUMARIN AND THIOCOUMARIN DERIVATIVES

Methanol %	20	40	60
$\Delta \mu^\ddagger$ (CO) ^a (kJ mol^{-1})	-0.9	-3.3	-5.8
$\Delta \mu^\ddagger$ (COC ⁻) ^b (kJ mol^{-1})	-0.4	-0.9	-1.3
$\Delta \mu^\ddagger$ (SCO) ^c (kJ mol^{-1})	-1.8	-5.0	-9.0
$\Delta \mu^\ddagger$ (SCOC ⁻) (kJ mol^{-1})	-2.5	-4.5	-6.3

^aCO = coumarin, data from Ref. 3. ^bCOC⁻ = coumarin-3-carboxylate, data from Ref. 3. ^cSCO⁻ = thiocoumarin, data from Ref. 17.

coumarin and thiocoumarin compounds have the same structure except that the first has C=O group and the second has C=S group.

The initial state-transition state analysis of the reactivity trends for 3-bromothiocoumarin and thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate anion are set out in Tables 3 and 6 and depicted in Figs. 2 and 3. Relatively small changes in single ion values can lead to significantly different conclusion concerning the relative importance of initial state and transition state contributions. This theme has been developed in relation to the base hydrolysis of thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate anion in aqueous methanol. It is now possible to illustrate the effects of different single ion assumptions in a quantitative manner. Detail of the initial state-transition state analyses of reactivity trends according to Abraham (TPTB) assumption¹¹ and the solvent-sorting procedure used by Wells^{15,16} are set out in Table 6 and illustrated in Figs. 3 and 4.

The results of Table 3 indicate that as the proportion of methanol increases, 3-bromothiocoumarin is significantly stabilised and the hydroxide

Fig. 2. Initial state-transition state analysis of base hydrolysis of 3-bromothiocoumarin in water-methanol mixture.

Fig. 3. Initial state-transition state analysis of base hydrolysis of thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate in water methanol mixtures, according to the single ion assumptions of Abraham (TPTB).

slightly destabilised, resulting the initial state being stabilised by changes in solvent composition. However, the transition state is unaffected on increasing the methanol content, and the decrease in rate constant can be attributed to the greater effect of the solvent on the initial state.

Fig. 4. Initial state - transition state analysis of base hydrolysis of thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate in water-methanol mixtures, according to single ion assumptions of Wells (solvent-sorting).

The results of Table 6 according to Abraham assumption (TPTB) show that thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate is markedly stabilised and hydroxide slightly destabilised as the alcohol content increases resulting in an overall increase in stabilisation of initial state on increasing the methanol content. On the other hand, the transition state is only slightly stabilised on transfer from water to 60% methanol. However, the initial state and transi-

Experimental

3-Bromothiocoumarin was prepared according to known method¹⁷. Thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate was prepared according to the following method.

Preparation of starting material: Coumarin-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester¹⁸ (4.36 g, 0.02 mol) was mixed with phosphorus pentasulphide (4 g, 0.02 mol) in dry toluene (50 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 h, then was evaporated to dryness and the residual solid was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–100°), (2.3 g, 50%), m.p. 100° (Found: C, 61.12; H, 4.10; S, 13.52. C₁₂H₁₀O₃S calcd. for: C, 61.53; H, 4.27; S, 13.67%).

Thiocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid: Thiocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (2.3 g, 0.01 mol) suspended in HCl (4 N; 50 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. After cooling, the resulting solid (1.8 g, 80%) was crystallised from water, m.p. 180° (Found: C, 57.96; H, 2.63; S, 15.31. C₁₀H₆O₃S calcd. for: C, 58.25; H, 2.91; S, 15.53%).

NaOH (AnalaR) stock solution was used. Ionic strength was maintained using NaCl (AnalaR) solution. Solvent mixtures were prepared by mixing known volumes of the pure liquids.

Kinetics of hydrolysis were monitored in 10 mm silica cells in the thermostated cell compartment using a Cecil 599 spectrophotometer.

The sparingly soluble thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate potassium and hexaaminocobalt(III) salts were prepared by double decomposition in alcohol-water mixtures. Solubility was measured by agitating a generous excess of solid with the appropriate

TABLE 6—INITIAL STATE—TRANSITION STATE ANALYSIS OF SOLVENT EFFECTS ON REACTIVITY TRENDS FOR THIOCOUMARIN-3-CARBOXYLATE ACCORDING TO TPTB AND WELLS

Methanol (% v/v)	TPTB			Wells		
	20	40	60	20	40	60
$\Delta \mu^\ddagger$ (SCOC ⁻) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-2.5	-4.5	-6.3	-0.8	-1.4	-1.3
$\Delta \mu^\ddagger$ (OH ⁻) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-0.2	0.1	1.6	1.8	3.8	6.9
$\Delta \mu^\ddagger$ (IS) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-2.7	-4.4	-4.7	1.0	2.4	5.6
$\Delta \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	1.1	2.3	3.4	1.1	2.3	3.4
$\Delta \mu^\ddagger$ (TS) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-1.6	-2.1	-2.1	2.1	4.7	9.0

tion state are stabilised on increasing the methanol content with the decrease in the rate constant determined by the greater effect of solvent on the initial state.

Using the transfer parameters given by Wells, one sees marked destabilisation of the hydroxide ion and slightly destabilisation of the thiocoumarin-3-carboxylate anion resulting in a marked stabilisation of the initial state and of the transition state as the methanol content of the mixture increases. The general initial state—transition state pattern does not depend on the single ion assumption used in the analysis, but the actual values for the transfer quantities depend markedly on the assumption used.

solvent mixture in a thermostated vessel for several hours. Portions of supernatant saturated solution were removed and centrifuged rapidly before withdrawing an aliquot, diluting as necessary, and measuring the absorbance for the salt in question.

References

- O. METH-COHN and TARNOWSKI, *Adv. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1980, 26, 148.
- J. BURGESS and E. A. ABU-GHARIB, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1984, 8.
- E. A. ABU-GHARIB, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1988, 6, 916.
- M. J. BLANDAMER, J. BURGESS and E. A. ABU-GHARIB, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1984, 9, 193.
- A. EL-SAMAHY, E. A. ABU-GHARIB, A. EL-TAHER and R. EL-KHATIB, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, 66, 808.
- M. J. BLANDAMER and J. BURGESS, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1979, 51, 2087; 1982, 54, 2285; 1983, 55, 55.

7. M. J. BLANDAMER and J. BURGESS, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1975, **4**, 55.
8. M. J. BLANDAMER and J. BURGESS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, **31**, 39.
9. S. GLASSTONE, K. J. LAIDLER and H. EYRING, "The Theory of Rate Processes", Mc-Graw-Hill, New York, 1941.
10. M. J. BLANDAMER, J. BURGESS and J. B. F. N. ENGBERTS, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1985, **14**, 237.
11. M. H. ABRAHAM, T. HILL, H. C. LING, R. M. SCHUTZ and R. A. C. WATT, *J. Chem. Soc., Farady Trans. 1*, 1984, **80**, 489.
12. M. J. BLANDAMER, J. BURGESS, B. CLARK, P. DUCE, A. W. HAKIN, N. GOSAL, S. RADULOVIC, P. GUARDADO, F. SANCHEZ, C. HUBBARD and E. A. ABU-GHARIB, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1986, **82**, 1471.
13. M. J. BLANDAMER, J. BURGESS and E. A. ABU-GHARIB, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1984, **9**, 234.
14. C. TISSIER, *C. R. Acad. Sci. Paris*, 1978, **286c**, 35
15. C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Farady Trans. 1*, 1973, **69**, 984.
16. C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Farady Trans. 1*, 1974, **70**, 694.
17. E. A. ABU-GHARIB and A. A. GHATTAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1988, **65**, 489.
18. A. SAMOUR and M. ALKADY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **51**, 12.